

Mapping elite sociability: using digital tools to recreate scientific networks in the Indian Academy of Sciences

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In a journal article in *Nature* from 2023, Ankur Paliwal succinctly makes the case that, in India, scientific communities still struggle even to the present day with questions of elitism in relation to caste. Elitism is an undeniable feature of scientific cultures in every part of the globe but, as Paliwal states, in India this elite scientific culture was augmented by a strict caste system and gender roles. While these are important factors for academics to analyse, they obscure other forms of elite scientific culture. This paper seeks to provide an insight into the less well-defined topic of elite sociability. Through examining this aspect, we can not only see a different side of elite existence but also explore how elitism practically manifested and was utilised. I also wish to use this paper as a preliminary exploration into how the concept of the elite was perceived and reacted to by those outside of the elite structures of power.

To provide context, when India became independent from British rule in 1947, its scientific community was divided. Divided by Partition, the caste system, economic inequality, language and gender but was also divided along more practical barriers. Before Indian Independence, there existed three competing organisations that styled themselves as the national academy of sciences for India: the Indian Academy of Sciences, the Indian National Science Academy (formerly the National Institute of Sciences India) and the National Academy of Sciences, India (referred to going forward as IAS, INSA and NASI respectively).

Many scientists were members of multiple academies at the same time and two of these academies, INSA and NASI, were founded principally by the same person, notable Indian scientist Meghnad Saha. All three produced scientific journals for the wider scientific community, both domestic and international, and organised their journals in resemblance to the style of the Royal Society. Yet, one critical

difference existed in the way the societies were organised. While INSA and NASI had presidents who served for a two-year term, the IAS had one President for the first 40 years of its existence. As a result, control of the society and the journal was concentrated in the hands of its founder, chairman and the first Asian winner of the Nobel Prize in Physics, C.V. Raman.

Due to this unique consolidation of authority, the case of the IAS provides the opportunity for an interesting study into the role that sociability played among Indian scientific elites and how that sociability manifested itself practically within the IAS and, more specifically for this paper, the journal of the IAS. Proceedings of the Indian Academy of Sciences was a monthly journal published between 1934 and 1977, comprised of sections A and B that focused on the physical and biological sciences respectively. While the journal went through a stylistic change and organised an editorial board in 1972, for much of its lifetime it had no standardised editorial guidelines or person in charge. Historians such as Abha Sur and Jahnavi Phalkey have argued that the organisation of the journal was run by C.V. Raman and a cadre of scientists close to him. As such, I hypothesise that the journal is a valuable source to identify important scientists, as indicators of influence can be seen within aspects of the journal.

I intend to use digital tools in order to analyse the journals. Since there are 876 issues of the journal within the premiership of C.V. Raman, each of those with between 3-15 papers per issue, it would be impossible to visualise this amount of data without the assistance of digital tools. I will build a relational database on the program NodeGoat in order to track links between different scientists through papers and communications and develop a network of connections between scientists in order to analyse individuals of key interest. I will then also analyse these links using social network analysis

methods in order to interpret the different aspects of the data I will plot.

One reason to do this is to more easily visualise large amounts of data and extrapolate connections that would have been difficult to see otherwise, but there is another benefit that come from using this method. For historians, access to sources and archives is a necessary component for understanding the full picture of a historical situation. For high profile elite scientists, such as C.V. Raman, access to those crucial documents is often restricted for a number of reasons. Through the recreation of networks via digital tools, I will be able to identify key individuals within these networks, for whom access to their documents may be less restricted.

There are two elements of the journal that I will be analysing. Firstly, there is the matter of publications. The lack of clarity regarding formal editorial control, contrasted with the number and longevity of the publication would reasonably lead to the idea that an informal method of submitting papers and having them published existed. This informal method could therefore be subject to personal bias, compared to a formal admission structure, thus allowing the elite group of scientists to use their influence to affect publication rates of other scientists. Reversely, rates of publication could serve as indicators of status and influence within scientific communities, thus ensuring that the influential continue to propagate their own authority and influence within the scientific community. However, lack of formal structures may be viewed from a different perspective when using a colonial and post-colonial framework.

As stated earlier, all the national academies styled their infrastructure and journals on the Royal Society in Britain. Notably this did not include peer review, a form of which, according to historian Aileen Fyfe, had emerged since the 1830s. Peer review was not universally adopted, as other academics point out. For example, the implementation of peer review was still a debated topic in the 1970s in the U.S., according to Melinda Baldwin. Thus, the rejection of peer review could be interpreted as a rejection of some of the more elitist elements of the Royal Society and instead adopting a much more open and fairer approach that allowed more scientists to get published, without having to conform to

institutional standards. While this paper does not seek to provide an answer to the question, it will provide data that can be useful in comparing scientific cultures internationally.

The second factor is who communicated the article itself. While some scientists presented their own papers, others had their papers communicated by another scientist within the academy and this was always displayed at the top of the publication. This process comes from the Royal Society, where a member would communicate papers on behalf of an author that was not a member and thus the communicator assume a degree of responsibility regarding the quality of the paper. By analysing this component of the journal, it will provide insight into the sociability of elite scientists outside of the IAS membership, as well as build up a picture regarding the networks of connections and influence between scientists. With publications and communications combined, this will create a network of formal connections that will indicate where informal connections are likelier to exist, thus allowing for more efficiency and accuracy when exploring for sources that would provide more evidence for informal connections.